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Basic Science as a Catalyst for Entrepreneurial Development at the Upper Basic Education Level in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Basic Science is one of the core subjects at the basic level of education. It aims to provide a sound base of both the process and skills of science as unified entity to young pupils at primary and junior secondary school levels. This paper examined Basic Science as a catalyst for entrepreneurial development at the Upper Basic Education level in Benue State, Nigeria. The article highlighted the nature and concept of the subject, brought out skills enshrined in Basic Science curriculum many of which are required and important entrepreneurially. It also discussed the effective methods of developing these important skills in our pupils which include child-centred, activity-based demonstration and excursion methods. The concepts of entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship education as well as entrepreneurial skills were also examined. The role of the Basic Science teachers in the

development of entrepreneurial skills in pupils at Upper Basic Education level in Benue State was looked into which included mastery of the subject matter, teacher ability to motivate the students, psychomotor skills of the teacher and managerial skills among others. The paper also examined the factors that militate against the development of entrepreneurial skills in Basic Science at the Upper Basic Education level such as inadequate teacher preparation, absence and poor laboratories as well as low level motivation of teachers. It was concluded that Basic Science played a vital role in the development of entrepreneurial skills at the Upper Basic Education level in Benue State. The paper recommended among others, that entrepreneurship education should be made part of science teachers' education at various level of education in Benue State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Basic Education, Basic Science, Basic Science Teachers, Entrepreneurship Development, Upper Basic Education,

Introduction

Science and Technology have long been recognized as the instruments par excellence for nation building and for wealth creation which made every country today craves for their advancement (Okoro, 2004; Ajewole, 2005 in Ataka and Okedeji, 2009). This has led to the promotion of scientific literacy for decades and therefore, in the current science-and technology dominated society, scientific literacy is considered as an important goal of science education (Shu-Nu-Chang, 2007). While scientific literacy is for enhancing individuals' scientific concepts, scientific attitudes and process skills towards science, it also aims at increasing international competition and creating a well-being modern life (Laugksch, 2000; Shu-Nu-Chang, 2007). Creating a well-being modern life implies among others, that individuals become productive and become happy with their situations.

One of the major challenges of science education is how to make it functional which is believed to be the secret of its success. In Nigeria and indeed all other developing countries this challenge has being most daunting. As a result of this and coupled with our desire to be successful, we need to create the right atmosphere necessary for functional science education in Nigeria. Although several factors could be required to achieve this very apt paradigm shift, developing entrepreneurial skills through the leaching and learning of science remains vital. Okafor (2006) in Mohammed and Funtua (2009) observed that, we need to create the right atmosphere that would create and develop the necessary skills in our students necessary for meaningful stride in Science and Technology.

The Nigerian government through its policy on education seriously supports the teaching and learning of science at all levels of education. Some of the precisions at lower level of education include (Federal Ministry of Education (FME), 2007):

- i. Lay a sound basis for scientific and reflective thinking
- ii. Give the pupil opportunities for developing manipulative skills
- iii. Provide the pupils with basic tools for further educational development

To achieve these laudable objectives, it has prescribed the inclusion of Basic Science in the curriculum of both Primary and Junior Secondary Schools (Basic level).

However, despite the fact that this very promising curricular area started way back in 1971, the desired result of our scientific and technological greatness is yet to be realized in Nigeria (Akpan, 2004). Though many reasons have been advanced to explain this worrisome situation, the fact remains that developing entrepreneurial skills through the teaching and learning of science (Basic Science being the foundation which serves as a catalyst for entrepreneurial development) is a must. Yes, we need to impart to the children scientific and technological skills to prepare them for functional science education if they are to really contribute to our national development through science and technology (Mohammed & Funtua, 2009). This need agrees with the opinion of Iwovi (2006) when he asserted that “it is a fact of modern times that functional education has become crucial for the survival of individuals and for the development of society. Unless a proper foundation is laid at the lower (basic) education level, much of what occurs at the other (upper) levels of education may not be sound, appropriate and appreciative”.

The Nature and Concept of Basic Science

Basic Science as in the new Science Education Curriculum has been developed from Integrated Science. Basic Science stresses to beginners the general principles which run through the entire world of science. In effect, all teachers who are to be trained to teach Basic Science must move away from discriminatory attitude towards any of the sciences. This means that Basic Science Curriculum eliminates the repetitions of subject matter from the various sciences (Biology, Chemistry and Physics).

The overall objectives of the Basic Science Curriculum at Upper Basic Education level include developing students' interest in science and technology to enable students to acquire basic knowledge and skills in science and technology, to enable students to apply the scientific and technological knowledge and skills to meet societal needs, to enable students to take advantage of the numerous career opportunities offered by science and technology (Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council - NERDC, 2007).

Several definitions were advanced for the foundation science now termed Basic Science. Arbon (2002) and Wasagu (2004) as cited in Mohammed and Funtua (2009) defined Integrated Science now Basic Science as a course or subject of study which is devised and presented in such a way that pupils gain the concept of the fundamental unity of science, the commonality of approach to problems of scientific nature and are helped to gain an understanding of the roles and functions of science in everyday life and the world in which they live. Bajah (2006) as cited in Mohammed and Funtua (2009) saw Basic Science as approaches in which the concepts and principles of science are presented so as to express the fundamental unity of scientific thought and to avoid premature or undue stress on the distinction between the various scientific fields. Basic Science and Technology is basic in scientific skills required for human survival, sustainable development and societal transformation.

The concept of Basic Science is based on the assumption (if not fact) that the universe has an inherent unity in which science attempts to provide knowledge for the

understanding of this unity (Okafor. 2007). Basic Science emphasizes those concepts which are common to all the sciences, the processes of science and its skills. It treated the great themes of science such as Energy, Force and Particles Theories, Conservations, Balance and Cycles in nature and more importantly brings out in clear terms the relevance of science in everyday life (Mohammed & Gwandu. 2008). Basic Science in the nutshell means teaching science (i.e. relevant knowledge in Biology, Chemistry, Physics, Mathematics, Geography and even Agricultural Science and Technology) in a unified form to enable students gain the functional unity of science (Ajeweie, 2005).

One of the major philosophies of Basic Science is that, the pupils at the basic level of education are not matured enough to appreciate the boundaries between the science disciplines of Biology, Chemistry and Physics. This it believes can only appear as artificial, man-made idea which seriously interferes with the unified view of nature as a whole and which the children bring to the classroom with them. Learning at this level should be by direct experience because by so doing the pupils will be motivated to acquire both academic and practical skills (Nneji. 2006). This is in quite agreement with the popular saying that: Hear and forget, See and remember, Do and understand.

It also agrees with the fact that science is a way of discovery through experimentation. One of the activities in science is experimentation. It provides a forum for practicalizing the theoretical knowledge gained in the classroom and demonstrating the psychomotor skill of a teacher and learner. It further aids the understanding of difficult concepts in curriculum, creates opportunity for the testing of facts and theories in sciences. It is believed that the learner can achieve more if given the opportunity to practicalise what he/she has been taught in the classroom. Experimentation thus gives room for better attainment of lesson objectives. Experimentation in science is however dependent on the availability of science equipment for its understanding, development and application (Ugwu, 2008). Accordingly, activities should form the basis of teaching Basic Science. If all teachers of this great foundation of science teach it experimentally several skills including entrepreneurial ones would definitely be developed in the pupils.

Entrepreneurship

According to Aminu (2008), entrepreneurship is the process of creating something new with value, by devoting the necessary time and effort, assuming the accompanying financial, psychic and social risks, and receiving the resulting rewards of monetary and personal satisfaction and independence. Nwoye in Ibrahim, Mandara and Soba (2008) defines entrepreneurship as the quality and characteristics normally expected as a successful entrepreneur. It includes perception of new economic opportunities, taking initiatives, creativity, and innovation, the ability to turn a given resources and situation to practical account and acknowledgement that failure is possible. On the other hand, Leebaert in Ezeudu (2008) defined entrepreneurship as a process of organizing, managing and assuming risk of a business. Thus, who should be an entrepreneur? The word entrepreneur originated from an Irish man called Cantillo in France in the early part of the 18th century (Aminu, 2008). The word entrepreneur in French is “*entreprenre*” literally translated to mean one who undertakes or one who is ‘between-taker or go between’.

Cantillo defines entrepreneurs as people who have the ability to see and evaluate business, gather the necessary resources to take advantage of them and initiate, appreciate action to ensure success. He argued that a typical entrepreneur is a risk taker, a man who braves uncertainty, strikes out on his own and through nature with devotion to duty and singleness of purpose, somehow create a business and industry activity where none existed before. This means an entrepreneur is any one or group of persons who create a business, establishes it and nurse it to growth and profitability or takes over an existing business with sole purpose of introducing new goods and services and developing new sources of materials and continues to build and innovate on it. This can best be achieved if individuals are given functional entrepreneurship education.

Entrepreneurship Education

Ojukwu in Ezeudu (2008) described entrepreneurship development as a programme of human capital development inputs aimed at increasing the supply of adequately trained entrepreneurs who are motivated to make a success out of business. Thus, entrepreneurship education is the education for end about business. Accordingly, Bolarinwa (2001) as cited in Ezeudu (2008) defined entrepreneurship education as education that provides training, experience and skills that are suitable for entrepreneurship endeavours. Entrepreneurship education therefore prepares JSS Basic Science graduates, both drop outs and continuing ones at upper basic education with entrepreneurial knowledge, competence and skills needed to be self-reliant. Therefore the development of entrepreneurial skills through Basic Science at the upper basic education is urgently required in view of the growing graduates unemployment and the many advantages which such education hold for the development of the country (Konyeme &Ukpene, 2009).

Entrepreneurship Skills

The Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary (Hornby, 2006) defines Entrepreneurial Skills as those skills required to start or run a business especially when the business involves taking financial risks. A good look through Basic Science Curriculum shows clearly that it is full of various skills required to be taught and learnt. It is expected that both process and products skills be acquired to enable the pupils master them and subsequently apply same in solving problems (including economic needs) for the improvement of both oneself and the general society. These skills through a series of activities are expected to be carefully designed and implemented. Although these skills are too many to be captured in total, the most important ones and more entrepreneurial ones include the following:

Observing	Classifying	Measuring
Recording	Drawing	Identifying
Selecting	Handling	Manipulating
Hypothesizing	Experimenting	Concluding
Generalizing	Predicting	Controlling
Cutting	Sketching	Tighting
Painting	Fitting	Screwing
Testing	Designing	Analyzing
Inspecting	Servicing	Dismantling
Assembling	Installing	Repairing

Most of these skills are observable behaviours which can be acquired through manipulation of tools, equipment and machines. As observed by Ivowi (2006), a skill is said to be developed or acquired if it can be demonstrated correctly at least in every 2 out of 3 occasions that demand it, at least for the sake of basic education. As can be observed, the skills are in hierarchy and even for a particular skill it has different levels of sophistication or difficulty. It is therefore the role of the teacher to ensure effective utilization of the provided opportunities so that he or she can develop sound skills in the pupils, many of which are entrepreneurial in nature.

Acquisition and development of Basic Science Entrepreneurial Skills at Upper Basic Education Level

Basic Science as a subject of study contributes to the development of society through cultivation of scientific culture. It is also educates future generations in the acquisition of necessary knowledge, skills and attitudes for coping with the ever demanding world of science and technology (Akinsola, Lawal & Oyedokun. 2009). Education in Basic Science is thus aimed at producing large, qualitative manpower that have good base in science and technology and generally a scientific literate society that can solve its own problems. Where entrepreneurial skill is added to the skill acquired in learning some concepts in Basic Science, it will help the pupils to acquire the mindset and know-how necessary to make self-employment a viable career option after graduation.

The teaching of some of these concepts that leans itself to entrepreneurial skill acquisition is done in such a way that the students/learners will develop and acquire innovative skills. Such skills are identifying, creating, initiating and successfully managing personal or community business and work opportunities. A look at the Basic Science curriculum reveals concepts that lean towards entrepreneurial skills acquisition. These can be identified and taught to the pupils at upper basic education in Benue State. This can be done in such that the students would acquire the inherent skills that can be used to set up business.

Basic Science Concepts or Courses that are taught at Upper Basic Education level in Benue State for Entrepreneurial Development

Some of the courses or concepts in Basic Science curriculum that are taught at upper basic education level in Benue State with the aim of injecting into the pupils/learners the entrepreneurial skills are presented in table1 below:

Table 1: Basic Science Concepts and Identified Entrepreneurial Skills

Basic Science Concepts	Entrepreneurial Skills	Theme in JSS Basic Science
1.Transport, control and development in living things (circulatory, excretory, nervous and skeletal systems)	Making models of: i. Human and other vertebrate ii. Kidney iii. Skull	You and technology
2.Components of the environment (characteristics of living things and its classification, cells, chromosomes and genes) ▪ Plant stems ▪ Cam wood ▪ Cocoa yam leaves ▪ Ginger root ▪ Cola-nuts (different types) Samples of natural objects viz ▪ Mountain ▪ Seeds/fruits ▪ Crayfish, crab, tortoise etc.	i. Extraction of colour and making paints ii. Nature drawings	You and environment (you as a living thing)
3.Mathematics for science	Constructing different ▪ Shapes of objects ▪ Rectangular, triangular, prism, cylindrical etc. ▪ Graduating rulers	You and technology
4.Man and the environment: special role of human being ecological concepts, influence of man on environment, pollution and conservation	Figure (life) i. Drawing ii. Basketry iii. Dyeing iv. Mat weaving v. Calabash craving vi. Making of fertilizer, pesticide vii. Paints from oil	You and technology You and environment

5.Reproduction and Growth	Model and figure drawing of i. Pregnant woman ii. Human reproductive system iii. Blastula iv. Gastrula v. Organogenesis	You and technology
6.Environmental pollution of the biosphere	i. Refuse disposal ii. Sewage disposal	You and environment
7.Sexual and asexual reproduction among plants	Raising of flower seedlings and orchards	You and technology

Source: Adapted from Ajewole, Alaka & Akedeyi (2009), and Basic Science Curriculum (2011), and modified by the researchers.

Basic Science in a general term refers to teaching science (that is. relevant knowledge of chemistry, biology, physics, agricultural science and technology, mathematics and even geography) in a unified form to enable students or learners gain the fundamental unity of science (Ajewole, 2005), Based on the above assertion, Ajewole *et al.* (2009) identify the following possible- areas for skill acquisition in science;

- i. Biology: biotechnology, basketry, mat weaving, cotton spinning, fishery, life drawing, etc.
- ii. Chemistry: soap making, dye production, wine brewing, disinfectants, perfumes, polish, bottled water, distilled water etc.
- iii. Physics: battery charging, electrical motor coil, re-wiring, vulcanizing
- iv. Mathematics: designing shapes of various sizes, calibrated ruler
- v. Agriculture: animal husbandry (poultry, rabbitary, snail farming, bee-keeping, fishery etc.), horticulture, floriculture, vegetable culture, etc.

How can these coping skills in the world be acquired by the students?

The newly packaged Basic Science and integrated science (ISC) curriculum in the junior secondary schools and tertiary institutions are careers of productivity-based one hinging on resourcefulness and creativity of students. It is therefore necessary for teachers/lecturers leaching Basic Science and integrated science to identify some life skills/entrepreneurial skills in the courses or in each ISC course. The teacher can then adopt activity-based methods in which a number of activities will be given to the pupils/students individually or in groups. Projects on the identified life skills can also be given to the students/pupils and submitted at a given time and date.

Emphasizing generic skills; while almost all entrepreneurship educators see a continuing need to train students in entrepreneurship-specific skills so that they can find employment upon graduation, there is increased interest in generic skills that are broadly transferable to almost any career (Ajewole, *et al.* 2009). Perhaps one of the best formulations of these generic skills is that which produced by Stasz, Mcarthur, Lewis & Ramsey (1990) in Ajewole, Alaka & Okedeyi. (2009) shown below;

Generic skills for changing work place Basic skills

- i. Reading with comprehension and critical judgment
- ii. Writing clearly and effectively
- iii. Mastering mathematical computations
- iv. Performing practical life skills e.g. reading a schedule or filing out an application

Complex reasoning and information processing skills (presented as a problem-solving process)

- i. Recognizing a problem
- ii. Analyzing the problem
- iii. Generating solution paths
- iv. Evaluating the paths of monitoring implementation
- v. Repairing using alternative actions
- vi. Reflecting about the process and the solution

Attitude and dispositions

- i. Ability to make decisions
- ii. Willingness to take responsibility for one's decisions
- iii. Willingness to be held in decision making
- iv. Learning the parameters of the workplace
- v. Cooperating with others.

The target is to equip all pupils with skills that will enable them function in changing economy and a changing workplace.

Methods of Developing Entrepreneurial Skills

The teacher is the key to any educational development. Therefore teachers of Basic Science must wake up to the challenge of developing in our pupils, the hope of tomorrow, the skills and competences necessary for our greatness as a nation. The time is just now. How science is taught and learnt form an index to increase the level of skills acquired. As a body of knowledge, science has acceptable methods through which skills in them could be acquired. Accordingly teachers as the main operators of educational programmes need not only to know them but also be able to demonstrate and use them when teaching their pupils (Nneji, 2006). There are several methods of developing skills which when fully utilized would develop in our pupils the required entrepreneurial skills necessary for our science and technological greatness as a nation. These include;

- i. Activity-based method
- ii. Problem solving method
- iii. Science-technology-society
- iv. Excursion method

If fully utilized, a combination of all or few of these can provide the necessary skills to our pupils. Teachers need to maximize much of, if not all of the above for as opined by Ivowi (2006). The world of works is very vast, complex and demanding and emphasized the need to expose pupils at the basic level of education through simple and concrete processes of science (and technology) rather than concentrating on their products.

In addition to the above listed methods of developing the required skills, there are other essential ingredients necessary for effective skills developments in children. These include:

- a. *Motivation*: The place of motivation in the educational delivery needs no emphasis. The teacher, therefore need to motivate his pupils to learn the necessary skills for future application in the entrepreneurial process. This motivation could be both intrinsic and extrinsic, the two of which are fully documented in education. Once a pupil is motivated by developing interest in him or her learning will surely follows.
- b. *Encouragement*: The teacher needs to encourage the development of entrepreneurial skills. These could be achieved through;
 - i. Provide child-friendly environment to the pupils
 - ii. Display a role model attitude to his pupils
 - iii. Provide ample activities for the pupils
 - iv. Expose the pupils to challenging opportunities
 - v. Provide times for explorations through excursion and its likes
- c. *Improvisation*: The nature of Basic Science shows clearly the costly nature of the subject if all the needed materials are to be provided. This reality of today make's such provision impossible in most cases. This couple to the problem of damages and insufficient power supply in Nigeria more than ever before call for improvisation. Enjayeju (1983) as cited in Mohammed and Funtua (2009) defined improvisation as whenever there is a lack or shortage of some specific first hand teaching aids. Improvisation is art act of creativity and is of three levels (Nneji, 2006) which are;
 - i. Use of more substitutes, example using transparent tumbler as a beaker.
 - ii. Creation of substitute, examples a model creation, drawing of chart
 - iii. Original creation, example a teacher using locally source materials to produce a tool/equipment which replaces what used to be imported or purchased at very high cost.

Entrepreneurial Skills for self-reliance in Basic Science

The JSS 3 Basic Science graduates should be able to undertake the production of the followings on commercial scale for self-reliance and self-employment (Konyeme & Ukpene, 2009).

- i. Animal production skills for example, fish farming, rabbitary, poultry production, animal fattening etc.
- ii. Cross breeding skills through artificial insemination
- iii. Instructional materials production, for instance production of models and charts as improvisation
- iv. Identification and marketing of medical plants
- v. Horticulture, example flower gardens maintenance
- vi. Food and water quality skills
- vii. Food and beverages production skills example fermentation of beverages, cheese.

The Role of the Basic Science Teachers in Developing Entrepreneurial Skills in Pupils at the Upper Basic Education Level

Basic Science teachers play a profound role in influencing and helping pupils develop the following:

i) Mastery of subject matter

Teachers need to understand a subject enough to convey its essence to learners/students. This is to establish a sound knowledge-base on which students will be able to build as they are exposed to different life experiences. Good teachers can translate information, good judgment, experience and wisdom into relevant knowledge that a student can understand, retain and pass to others. Basic Science promotes exchange of knowledge, experience and approaches to nation building.

ii) Teachers ability to motivate students

Achieving success on any endeavor depends on the person's willingness to pursue it in spite of the obstacles. Teachers have their responsibility of motivating the students to be willing to pursue opportunities once identified. There are several human motivations that influence the entrepreneurship process thereby developing the skills. Activities that will motivate students to be involved in value creation should be introduced. These activities should show that students' contributions are valued. A good basic -science teacher should be able to develop, nurture and sustain an entrepreneurship spirit among pupils (Leis, Awobodu & Adegbamigbe, 2009).

iii) Psychomotor Skill of the Teacher

It is a known fact that Basic Science teachers should be able to connect what is being taught in the class to the real world situation. The level of retention is at the highest when pupils do or practice what they have been taught than what they hear or just see.

iv) Availability of skilled personnel (teachers)

Perceptions and decisions making that are both entrepreneurship skills are shaped in the pupils by the availability and resourcefulness of Basic Science teachers.

v) Teacher's Managerial Skills

It is a big challenge to groom new entrepreneurs who are able to adapt to our changing environment, engage in new ventures, and share advantage with large enterprises and providing new job openings. Basic Science teacher should be able to manage his/her class and the pupils in such a way that as to exposed the pupils to ways of applying different skills acquired to his/her problem, provide him or her with the basic manipulative skills useful in ordinary life and basic skills in local thinking.

vi) Teacher's Experience ass Facilitating Teamwork

In order to develop entrepreneurship skills in pupils, teacher can organize community-based or out-of-classroom resources for the pupils. The community constitutes a natural environment for informal science learning as in sports fields, markets, hospitals, industries, zoo (Wellington, 1990 cited in Lesi, Awobodu & Adegbamigbe, 2009). These informal learning sites provide experiences that impact on students' enthusiasm for exploring the world that they bring to the formal classroom learning. Students having opportunity to interact with others and materials have a lot of potentials and advantages such as nurturing curiosity, improving motivation, attitudes etc. thereby enriching knowledge and enhancing cognitive retention which will make them self-reliance.

Factors militating against the Development of Entrepreneurial Skills through Basic Science at the Upper Basic Education level in Benue State

- i. Absence and poor laboratory facilities: most secondary schools in Nigeria do not have a Basic Science laboratory and those that have; the laboratories lack the necessary facilities for effective teaching and learning of the subject (Jongur, Lanah. Hassan & Shuaibu, 2006 cited in Jongur. Kabulu & Abba, 2009).
- ii. Inadequate Teacher Preparation: the Basic Science teachers are not adequately trained in entrepreneurship and cannot develop such skills in the pupils.
- iii. Low Level Motivation: teachers are not adequately motivated to teach effectively in order to develop the right type of entrepreneurial skills in the pupils.
- iv. Teachers' Attitude to Work: teachers' lukewarm attitude towards work sometimes is due to poor environment of work and this can also affects entrepreneurial skill development.
- v. Teachers' Lack of improvisational Skills and the use of Variety: Improvisation in the view of Samba and Eriba (2011) is an act. It is a deliberate act that deals with the construction of instructional materials from locally available materials that can adequately replace or function in place of the original material which otherwise may be very expensive, in short supply or unavailable. Improvisation therefore is not just an un-pre-conceived on the spot activity. Improvisation is a state of mind and it is a skill that lies at the heart of good science teaching.

- vi. Lack of qualified Basic Science teachers: Basic Science teachers in Nigeria remain the only hope for improving science learning in both lower and upper basic education. But unfortunately, they are in short supply for the task at hand. Also, many of classroom Basic Science teachers are inexperienced, untrained and, in some cases, unqualified for the job they do (Oludipe, 1997 as cited in Oludipe, 2011).

These factors are also applicable in Benue State, Nigeria.

Implication of this paper to Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition

The discussion in this paper shows that Basic Science education holds the key to sustainable development. The implication of this is that if the Basic Science curriculum is irrelevant to the needs of the learner specifically and that of the society as a whole, and if the curriculum is developed without integrating life-related issues or career specific skills and be a career productivity based on the intention of the Federal Government to create job and reduce unemployment, create wealth, reduce poverty and re-oriented their values will be mirage. It is therefore the responsibility of the Basic Science teachers to identify these life-related issues in each course adopt guiding discovery and problem-solving approaches. Efforts should be placed on the utilitarian aspects of every Basic Science Education taught and the corresponding knowledge, values, skills and attitudes. Efforts should also be made by teachers to provide learning experiences that would enable school leavers to create job for themselves instead of searching for one.

Conclusion

The need to develop Entrepreneurial Skills in pupils at upper basic education level has remained a necessity in Nigeria considering our level of unemployment and abundant opportunities we are endowed with as a nation. To achieve this, science and technology education occupies central position, for they form the key to any meaningful development in Nigeria. Basic Science a core subject in the basic education provides the foundation levels of all the sciences and is full of the relevant entrepreneurial skills adequate for any successful entrepreneurship. Teachers of this all important subject should do everything possible to effectively develop entrepreneurial skills in their pupils so that both the dropouts and continuing ones can have the needed basic skills necessary for self-reliance, job creation and overall development of Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made from the deliberations of this paper:

- i. Entrepreneurship education should be made part of science teachers' education at various level of education in Benue State, Nigeria.
- ii. Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) and sister organizations should organize regular workshops, seminars and talks on entrepreneurial skill acquisition and development for their members.
- iii. Investment in research should be encouraged because through it knowledge expands and innovations emerge.

- iv. Conducive Regulatory Environment: effective government legislation should be made to encourage small scale enterprises to facilitate the emergence of young entrepreneurs.
- v. Credit Facilities: the issue of collateral has made accessing of loans by young entrepreneurs difficult if not impossible. Therefore, that should be removed to make loans readily available.

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